

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Down the TikTok rabbit hole of mental health misinformation: a content analysis of misinformation about mental disorder symptoms in TikTok videos

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Index

Abstract	2
Introduction	3
Methods	7
Results	13
Discussion	23
References	27
Appendix	30

Abstract

Objective: Young adolescents are increasingly using TikTok to search for information about mental health. The spread of misinformation about symptoms of mental disorders on TikTok can contribute to incorrect and harmful self-diagnosis by young people. This study aims to evaluate the quality and reliability of TikTok videos about symptoms of 10 mental disorders (major depressive disorder, bipolar disorder, borderline personality disorder, narcissistic personality disorder, post-traumatic stress disorder, social anxiety disorder, agoraphobia, obsessive compulsive disorder, dissociative identity disorder, schizophrenia).

Method: This quantitative content analysis included 315 TikTok videos that were coded for symptoms, creator identity, presentation of the information in the video, and user engagement. To assess the reliability of the symptoms, symptoms were compared to the DSM-V-TR criteria for psychiatric disorders.

Results: In this study, 41% of the mental disorder symptoms mentioned in TikTok videos were not a part of the DSM-V-TR criteria. Incorrect symptoms were either highly specific or extremely broad behaviors. Additional criteria for duration and impact on functioning of the symptoms were rarely mentioned in the videos. Furthermore, only 29% of the videos were posted by mental health professionals. Notably, there were significant differences in results between the included mental disorders.

Conclusion: This study showed that there is a considerable amount of inaccurate information presented in TikTok videos about mental disorder symptoms, resulting in a misleading and oversimplified representation of mental disorders. This potentially increases the risk of self-diagnosis among young adolescents.

Keywords: health communication, mental health, misinformation, social media

Introduction

The adolescent mental health crisis & the role of mental health literacy

The mental health of young people has become a topic of growing concern around the world. A large proportion of mental health issues arises before the age of 25 (Jones, 2013; Solmi et al., 2021). Over the past decade, the general mental well-being of adolescents (aged 10-19) has declined, with increasing rates of anxiety, depression, and suicidal thoughts (World Health Organization, 2022). Psychological issues experienced during adolescence can have long-lasting effects in adulthood, potentially resulting in adolescents facing a lifelong challenge with debilitating symptoms and a significant burden on society's rising healthcare costs (Fichter et al., 2009; Westberg et al., 2022).

One way to support struggling adolescents is to increase their mental health literacy (MHL). MHL is a concept derived from the domain of health literacy and is introduced by Jorm et al. (1997) as 'knowledge and beliefs about mental disorders which aid their recognition, management or prevention'. This conceptual framework consists of several components, defined as 'the ability to recognize specific disorders or different types of psychological distress, attitudes which facilitate recognition and appropriate help-seeking, and knowledge and beliefs about causes, treatment, and how to seek mental health information' (Jorm et al., 1997, p.182). Research shows that MHL is generally low among adolescents, which is associated with poorer mental health outcomes (Guo et al., 2023; Lam, 2014; Renwick et al., 2022). Many adolescents have difficulty in recognizing mental disorders and often hold incorrect beliefs about their causes and treatment (Guo et al., 2023). As a result, these adolescents may struggle to cope with personal problems and negative emotions, which causes them to adopt ineffective and unhealthy coping mechanisms. They are less likely to seek professional help and thus do not receive adequate treatment and support for their mental health problems.

Numerous studies are exploring how improving MHL can help combat the concerning rise of mental health problems among adolescents (Nobre et al., 2021). One strategy is to provide adolescents with accurate information about mental health, including symptoms, causes, and treatments. According to the MHL framework, increased knowledge can improve the recognition of mental disorders, prevent worsening of symptoms, and enable adequate intervention (Jorm, 2000). A potential approach to enhance MHL among adolescents that is currently being explored is reaching them through social media (Kruzan et al., 2022; O'Reilly et al., 2019).

Social media use among young adolescents & mental health content

One of the key characteristics of the current generation of young people is that they grew up with internet, smartphones, and social media. Adolescents frequently use social media platforms such as

TikTok, Instagram, and Snapchat (Pew Research Center, 2023). TikTok, in particular, is a popular platform among adolescents: it has a significant user base of adolescents, with 25% of TikTok users in the US aged between 10-19 years old and almost 50% under 30 years old (Howarth, 2024). According to Pew Research Center (2023), TikTok was used by 63% of American teenagers in 2023, surpassing Instagram and Snapchat in terms of user numbers and usage intensity among adolescents.

One particularly interesting aspect of TikTok is that it not only serves as a platform for social interaction with peers, but also as a source of information for young adolescents. Social media has become the predominant platform for news and health-related information among young people (Lupton, 2021). Research on news consumption habits shows that adolescents in the UK prefer social media platforms, particularly TikTok and Instagram, as sources of information over traditional news outlets like newspapers, radio, and search engines (Ofcom, 2023). Additionally, Hall & Partners (2023) found that globally, 33% of young adolescents turns to social media for health-related advice, with TikTok being the most popular platform.

The use of TikTok as source of information presents a significant risk, given the prevalence of misinformation on TikTok. Recent research by PlushCare (2022) has shown that there is a significant amount of misinformation about mental health circulating on TikTok. Up to 84% of mental health advice on TikTok is misleading, with videos containing inaccuracies and unverified health claims about mental disorder causes, symptoms, and treatment. Moreover, since any registered user is allowed to upload videos on TikTok, mental health content is not always posted by creators with verified medical credentials. According to PlushCare (2022), only 9% of mental health content creators on the platform hold a relevant medical certification, meaning that nine out of ten creators are not trained and qualified to give proper mental health advice.

Videos from unqualified creators frequently encourage self-diagnosis of disorders based on the inaccurate information they distribute about mental disorders and their associated symptoms. These videos often oversimplify mental illnesses by presenting common and broad symptoms that occur in different mental disorders as definite indicators of one specific disorder. Mentioning symptoms that do not necessarily have to indicate psychopathology on their own can result in medicalization of normative behavior among viewers (Rutter et al., 2023). Individuals lacking medical expertise are often unable to accurately determine whether they meet the diagnostic criteria for a specific disorder or not due to the sheer complexity and nuances involved in diagnosing mental disorders (Wakefield, 2010). As a result, these inaccurate and oversimplified videos can lead viewers to mistakenly diagnose themselves because they relate to the symptoms mentioned in the videos (Nguyen et al., 2023; PlushCare, 2022).

Additionally, self-diagnosing can be particularly harmful for viewers if it leads to misdiagnosis. Inaccurate and potentially harmful advice from unqualified creators can result in users making

inappropriate self-treatment decisions and prevent them from receiving adequate medical care. In addition, labeling oneself with a mental disorder can result in unnecessary emotional distress and unhelpful behavior, for example when people use it to justify their own poor behavior without any desire for change or accountability (Ahmed & Stephen, 2017). The spread of misinformation also contributes to further stigmatization of mental health, as it reinforces stereotypical perceptions of mental disorders and places an extra burden on an already overwhelmed mental healthcare system (Rutter et al., 2023; Simmons et al., 2017).

Theoretical framework: Attribution Theory & Selective Exposure Theory

This TikTok trend of self-diagnosing mental disorders can be linked to the attribution theory. Attribution theory describes how individuals explain causes of behavior by attributing them to specific circumstances (Banerjee et al., 2020). These beliefs about causes of behavior (attributions) can influence an individual's understanding of their own behavior. Misinformation on social media can lead people to adopt inaccurate beliefs about mental health problems (Banerjee et al., 2020). If someone encounters misinformation linking a specific mental health symptom that they recognize in themselves to a particular mental disorder, they may incorrectly attribute their own experiences and behaviors to that disorder. Individuals seeking an explanation for their problems then may assert that they have this particular disorder, without evaluation and confirmation from a mental health professional.

This attribution process could then be reinforced by confirmation bias, as explained by the selective exposure theory (Lazarsfeld et al., 1968; Sears & Freedman, 1967). This theory entails that individuals tend to actively seek, interpret, and remember information that aligns with their pre-existing beliefs, thereby confirming these beliefs (confirmation bias). In the case of TikTok, users choose to engage with videos that confirm their beliefs and often scroll past videos that challenge them. On top of that, TikTok's algorithm provides users with a personalized feed by monitoring the content a user likes to watch to continuously provide users with content that optimally retains their attention (Harriger et al., 2022). In this way, the algorithm further reinforces attributions by exposing individuals to a continuous stream of similar content and accelerating them into a rabbit hole of increasingly unmoderated content (Harriger et al., 2022). This creates a filter bubble, where users are continuously provided with similar content, reinforcing their pre-existing beliefs in an endless loop of misinformation (Zimmer et al., 2019). If individuals already hold certain incorrect attributions regarding mental illness, exposure to misinformation on TikTok about particular symptoms of mental disorders can therefore increase people's likelihood of accepting such misinformation, as it aligns with their already existing beliefs (Zollo, 2019).

Objectives

Given that TikTok is a relatively new platform, there has been limited research on the prevalence of mental health-related videos on the platform. Especially research on misinformation about specific mental disorders is scarce. A recent study by PlushCare (2022) revealed that over 80% of TikTok videos providing mental health advice contained inaccuracies, with videos on ADHD, bipolar disorder, depression, and anxiety being the most inaccurate. Furthermore, studies conducted by Yeung et al. (2022) and Aragon-Guevara et al. (2023) found that more than 50% of TikTok videos discussing ADHD and autism contained misinformation. Other recent studies by Tadross & Griffin (2023) and Munoz et al. (2024) reported a substantial amount of misleading information about obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) and dissociative identity disorder (DID) on TikTok. These studies, however, primarily focused on the reliability of information about these disorders in general, including information about their causes and treatments. Little research has been done that specifically evaluates the accuracy of mental disorder symptoms presented in TikTok videos.

Meanwhile, the potential harm of TikTok's self-diagnosis trend on the mental health of adolescents is growing every day. To support struggling adolescents, it is necessary to investigate how to effectively provide young people with accurate information on mental health to combat these misconceptions and improve their mental health literacy. Therefore, further research is urgently needed to assess the reliability of information on mental disorder symptoms presented in TikTok videos to help identify the misconceptions adolescents may learn, as well as the popularity of these videos and the sources of misinformation on the platform. This research project aims to contribute to this goal by evaluating the quality and reliability of information about symptoms of mental disorders in TikTok videos with the following research questions:

RQ1: To what extent do TikTok videos on mental health contain misinformation about symptoms of mental disorders, and what are the current trends within misinformation?

RQ2: Do creators without mental health expertise post more misinformation about symptoms of mental disorders on TikTok than creators with mental health expertise?

RQ3: Do TikTok videos that contain misinformation about symptoms of mental disorders have more engagement than videos without misinformation?

Methods

Research method

A quantitative content analysis was conducted on English TikTok videos that presented a list of symptoms of 10 specified mental disorders. The disorders were selected based on their prevalence on TikTok and the degree of misinformation and stigmatization about these specific disorders in society (Cattloor et al., 2015; Kumar et al., 2020; Saleh, 2023). As the focus of this study is on young adolescents, disorders that typically manifest before this age, such as neurodevelopmental disorders (e.g., ADHD, autism), were excluded. Additionally, eating disorders were excluded due to the proactive measures taken by TikTok to remove eating disorder-related content from the platform. Furthermore, the included subtypes of anxiety disorders were selected with the condition that the official name of the disorder was used in the videos, as anxiety is frequently discussed on TikTok but is often referred to as ‘anxiety disorder’ instead of, for instance, ‘generalized anxiety disorder.’

The prevalence of the included disorders on TikTok was determined by the frequency of the hashtags used to reference these specific diagnoses. For each disorder, a list of potential hashtags was generated through an inspection of the videos and hashtags about the disorder on TikTok. The frequency of the use of the hashtags was determined by using a website that provides statistical data on the number of views for each hashtag (tiktokhashtags.com) and a TikTok scraper (TikTok Hashtag Scraper, Apify 2024). See also table 1 and appendix A. The most frequently used hashtag for each disorder was used to compare and select the following ten disorders: major depressive disorder, bipolar disorder, borderline personality disorder, narcissistic personality disorder, post-traumatic stress disorder, obsessive compulsive disorder, dissociative identity disorder, schizophrenia, social anxiety disorder, and agoraphobia.

Privacy and ethics

According to TikTok guidelines, public videos on TikTok may be legally used for research purposes (TikTok, 2023). However, given that the creators of the TikTok videos that are included in this content analysis may be minors, any personal data that can be traced back to the video creator (username, video URL) has been stored in a separate file, accessible only to the primary researcher.

Data collection

Search terms

The search terms that were used for the collection of videos about the disorders were derived from the most frequently used hashtags for each disorder, which can be found in [table 1](#). These hashtags were then combined with the hashtag #symptoms. The search term for each disorder thus consisted of #disorderX #symptoms.

Table 1. The included 10 mental disorders (highest to lowest number of posts per hashtag)

	Disorder	Abbreviation	Most used hashtag	Hashtag posts	Hashtag views
1	Major depressive disorder	MDD	#depression	2.7 million	19.5 billion
2	Borderline personality disorder	BPD	#bpd	1.7 million	14.1 billion
3	Post-traumatic stress disorder	PTSD	#ptsd	1.2 million	8.5 billion
4	Narcissistic personality disorder	NPD	#narcissist	1.1 million	14.2 billion
5	Bipolar disorder	BD	#bipolar	914.2 thousand	6.4 billion
6	Dissociative identity disorder	DID	#did*	712.8 thousand	3.4 billion
7	Obsessive compulsive disorder	OCD	#ocd	350.2 thousand	7.7 billion
8	Social anxiety disorder	SAD	#socialanxiety	261.4 thousand	3.4 billion
9	Schizophrenia	SP	#schizophrenic	83.1 thousand	2.1 billion
10	Agoraphobia	AP	#agoraphobia	29.6 thousand	263.6 million

*Order based on number of posts of the most used hashtag per disorder as measured on 29/04/2024. * = This number of posts and views is probably an overestimation, as 'did' is a commonly used English word, so probably not all videos will be about dissociative identity disorder.*

Algorithm

In order to minimize the influence of TikTok's algorithmic bias on data collection, a new TikTok account was created. As the focus of this research is on young adolescents, the account was created with the date of birth of a 15-year-old (01/01/2009). During the data collection process, videos were being searched using the search function with the personalized search option switched off. A set number of videos per disorder were collected for seven consecutive days (13 July – 19 July 2024) at the same time every day (9 AM) to account for the potential impact of the time and day of the week on the search results. For the five most frequently discussed disorders (MDD, BPD, PTSD, NPD, BD), six videos were included per day. For the other five disorders (DID, OCD, SAD, SP, AP), three videos were included per day.

Video screening & storage

Videos were included on the condition that they presented a list of symptoms of one of the 10 selected mental disorders. The selection included both general videos as well as those created using the ‘photo mode’ feature on TikTok. Videos were excluded if they focused on a particular subgroup of the disorder (e.g., high-functioning depression), if the language was non-English, or if it was a duplicate video. If a video that had already been included on a prior day reappeared during the data collection process, the next suitable video was included. Descriptive characteristics including video URL, username, and the number of likes, comments, shares, and saves were manually gathered and registered on the day of video inclusion. The URLs were assigned a unique ID at the time of inclusion and stored in a master file. For privacy reasons, retraceable personal information (username, video URL) and corresponding IDs were stored separately and are only accessible to the primary researcher.

Figure 1. Flowchart of video screening process

Procedure

Codebook

A codebook was developed using both deductive and inductive coding. A pre-defined set of codes based on the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5-TR) for diagnosing mental disorders and based on existing content analyses on misinformation about video-based health communication on TikTok was created (American Psychiatric Association, 2022; Aragon-Guevara et al., 2023; Yeung et al., 2022). Following pilot testing, additional codes were added to clarify if necessary. An overview and descriptions of the included variables can be found in table 2. The complete code book is included in appendix B.

Table 2. Codebook variables

Coding category	Variables	Description
Symptoms	Included symptoms	All the symptoms that are mentioned in the video Categorization into DSM groups (criteria, manifestations, not in DSM) Categorization into symptom categories (i.e., cognitive, emotional, behavioral, social, physical, sleep/eat/self-care related, coping mechanisms)
	Number of symptoms	Total number of symptoms mentioned in the video
	Explanation of symptoms	Are symptoms simply summed up without further explanation or does the creator give a further description or specific examples?
	Word reference	Words that are used to refer to the symptoms in the video (e.g., symptoms, signs)
Other diagnostic criteria	Duration criterium	Is the minimum duration that symptoms should be present mentioned in the video?
	Severity criterium	Is significant impact on functioning mentioned as a criterium in the video?
Context	Individual/generalized context*	Does the creator mention symptoms of the disorder in general or is the creator talking about their personal experience?
	Target group	Is the video about a specific target group?
	Co-morbidity*	Does the video mention co-morbidities?
	Causes*	Does the video mention causes of the disorder?
	Treatments*	Does the video mention possible treatments?
Creator	Identity	What is the identity of the creator?
	Occupation	If (mental) health related: what is the occupation of the creator?
	Creator expertise	What is the expertise of the creator?
	Use of sources	Does the creator use sources?
Disclaimer	About dangers of self-diagnosis	Does the creator discourage self-diagnosis?
	About personal experience	In case of individualized context: does the creator mention that this is their personal experience and thus not generalizable?
	About not being qualified to give mental health advice	In case of unqualified creator: does the creator mention that they are not qualified to give mental health advice?
Video characteristics	Setting*	Are the symptoms mentioned in a funny/serious context?

*Variables marked with * are not included in the data analysis and results due to limited space.*

Fact-checking

In order to evaluate the reliability of the information regarding mental disorder symptoms in the videos, the symptoms were compared with the official diagnostic criteria for psychiatric disorders that are currently employed by clinicians for diagnosing mental disorders, outlined in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5-TR) (American Psychiatric Association, 2022). In order to quantify the degree of misinformation, the symptoms were assigned to one of three levels of

accuracy according to the DSM: (1) DSM criteria: the official symptom criteria as stated in the DSM-5-TR; (2) Manifestations of DSM criteria: symptoms that are not DSM criteria, but are direct manifestations of the DSM criteria AND are mentioned in the disorder's 'Diagnostic Features' or 'Associated Features' section in the DSM-5-TR textbook; (3) Non-DSM: symptoms that are neither DSM criteria nor in the extra text in the DSM. In order to also analyze videos on video-level rather than symptom-level, the percentage of symptoms in the video that belonged to each of the three groups was calculated per video. These groups will be referred to as 'DSM groups' throughout the rest of this manuscript.

Coding reliability

Prior to coding all videos, a sample of 10% was coded independently by the primary researcher and a second coder to assess inter-coder variability. The percentage agreement was calculated as a measure of agreement between the two coders. The minimum agreement rate was >80%, as this is generally considered to be a reliable rate according to *'The Content Analysis Guidebook'* (Neuendorf, 2002). In instances where this minimum agreement was not achieved, the coders discussed the discrepancies until they reached a consensus. All variables demonstrated sufficient intercoder reliability coefficients, which ranged from .81 to 1.00. Amendments to the codebook consisted of alterations to the wording and addition of clarifications of coding instructions. The primary researcher then proceeded to code the remaining videos.

To assess the influence of the algorithm on the selection of videos, the second coder also created a new TikTok account and used the same search terms to include five videos for each disorder. The 50 videos selected by the second coder were then compared with the videos included by the primary researcher. Of the 50 videos selected by the second coder, 26 (52%) videos were included by the primary coder on the first day of data collection, and 42 (84%) videos were included throughout the entire data collection period.

Data analysis

Descriptive statistics and non-parametric tests for non-normally distributed data were performed using the R statistical software (version 4.0.3) and the IBM SPSS Statistics software (version 29). The Mann-Whitney test was used to compare the DSM group percentages between independent, non-parametric samples, to test whether there was an association between the absence of explanation of symptoms in the videos and the prevalence of symptoms that are not part of the DSM. Furthermore, Mann-Whitney tests were used to determine whether there was a relation between the level of mental health expertise of creators and the percentages of symptoms in the three DSM groups. Spearman's

rank correlation coefficient was used as a non-parametric correlation measure to assess the relationship between the DSM group percentages and the user engagement metrics, to test whether incorrect symptoms were associated with higher user engagement. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. In instances where multiple testing was conducted, a Bonferroni correction was applied to determine the significance threshold for the p-value.

Results

Video characteristics

A total number of 315 TikTok videos presenting symptoms of the 10 specified mental disorders were selected (figure 2a). For the five most prevalently discussed disorders, 42 videos per disorder were included (MDD, BPD, PTSD, NPD, and BD). For the other five disorders, 21 videos per disorder were included (DID, OCD, SAD, SP, and AP). Figure 2b shows the median number of views per disorder, ordered from highest to lowest. A comparison of these view counts with those derived from the prior hashtag inspection (see table 1) indicates a discrepancy in the ordering of the mental disorders. In particular, the data indicates that videos about SAD in this dataset received considerably higher view counts than expected from the prior hashtag inspection, while videos about PTSD received considerably lower view counts. This could suggest that videos about SAD more frequently discuss the symptoms of this disorder, whereas videos about PTSD less frequently do so. This is because the prior hashtag inspection was based on all videos with that particular hashtag, whereas this analysis is based on a subset of videos about only the symptoms of the disorder.

Figure 2. Overview of number of views per disorder (A) & number of included symptoms per disorder (B)

Table 3. Overview of included disorders

Abbreviations	Disorders	Disorder category
MDD	Major depressive disorder	Mood disorder
BPD	Borderline personality disorder	Personality disorder
PTSD	Post-traumatic stress disorder	Trauma/stressor related disorder
NPD	Narcissistic personality disorder	Personality disorder
BD	Bipolar disorder	Mood disorder
DID	Dissociative identity disorder	Dissociative disorder
OCD	Obsessive compulsive disorder	Obsessive compulsive and related disorders
SAD	Social anxiety disorder	Anxiety disorder
SP	Schizophrenia	Psychotic disorder
AP	Agoraphobia	Anxiety disorder

DSM groups

All videos combined gave a dataset of 2199 symptoms, which were then compared to the official DSM-5-TR criteria. The dataset was divided into a total number of 1295 DSM criteria (59%), 445 manifestations of DSM criteria (20%), and 459 symptoms that are not included in the DSM at all (21%). See figure 3a for the distribution of the DSM groups per disorder. As the number of videos collected per disorder differed, figure 3b shows the distribution of the three DSM groups per disorder in percentages, ordered from the highest number of non-DSM symptoms for SAD (43%) to the lowest number for SP (9%). In the majority of the ten disorders, most of the included symptoms corresponded with the official DSM criteria. Only for SAD, NPD, and DID were DSM manifestations or non-DSM symptoms more prevalent.

Figure 3. The distribution of the three DSM groups per disorder, in order from the highest to lowest percentage of non-DSM symptoms (in red). A = symptom count; B = percentage of all symptoms.

Table 4 displays several examples of symptoms per DSM group that were mentioned in videos about MDD. Symptoms that were not included in the DSM were often highly specific behaviors or situations, such as “*looking for your phone first thing in the morning when you wake up*”. Moreover, the symptoms that were not included in the DSM frequently encompassed broad behaviors, such as a “*messy room*” or “*not answering texts*”.

Duration & severity criteria mentioned in video

In addition to a list of symptoms, the DSM criteria also include a specification of the minimum duration and severity of the listed symptoms. In the whole dataset, the criterium of minimum duration of the symptoms was mentioned in only 21 of the 315 videos (6.7%). The criterium of severity and significant impact on functioning was mentioned in only 8 out of 315 videos (2.5%). See table 5 for results per disorder.

Table 4. Examples of symptoms of Major Depressive Disorder per DSM group

DSM criteria	<i>"Persistent feelings of sadness"</i> <i>"Loss of interest in activities"</i>
Manifestations of DSM criteria	<i>"Social withdrawal"</i> <i>"Unexplained physical aches and pains"</i> <i>"Not showering or brushing teeth anymore"</i> <i>"Slacking off at work or school"</i>
Not in DSM	<i>"Looking at your phone first thing in the morning"</i> <i>"Messy room"</i> <i>"Not answering texts"</i> <i>"Drinking alcohol in the morning"</i>

Table 5. Overview of variables concerning the presentation of symptoms in TikTok videos

Disorder	Number of symptoms in video	Duration criterium mentioned	Functioning criterium mentioned	Symptoms explained	Target group mentioned
	Median (IQR)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)
Total	6 (4-9)	21 (6.7%)	8 (2.5%)	131 (41.6%)	32 (10.2%)
MDD	6 (5-9)	2 (4.8%)	0	9 (21.4%)	7 (16.7%)
BPD	6,5 (4-9)	2 (4.8%)	1 (2.4%)	20 (47.6%)	3 (7.1%)
PTSD	5 (4-8,25)	1 (2.4%)	1 (2.4%)	10 (23.8%)	0
NPD	5 (4-9)	3 (7.1%)	1 (2.4%)	29 (69.0%)	16 (38.1%)
BD	7 (4-10)	7 (16.7%)	0	10 (23.8%)	0
DID	5 (4-8)	1 (4.8%)	3 (14.3%)	11 (52.4%)	2 (9.5%)
OCD	6 (3-9)	0	0	10 (47.6%)	3 (14.3%)
SAD	5 (3,5-6)	2 (9.5%)	1 (4.8%)	10 (47.6%)	0
SP	6 (4-9)	2 (9.5%)	0	13 (61.9%)	1 (4.8%)
AP	5 (3-6)	1 (4.8%)	1 (4.8%)	9 (42.9%)	0

Abbreviations: IQR = interquartile range; N = number

Symptom categorization

All 2199 symptoms were assigned to different symptom categories, as can be seen in figure 4. This illustrates that, within the entire dataset, cognitive (36.1%), emotional (30.9%) and behavioral (28.2%) symptoms were mentioned most frequently. Examples of cognitive symptoms include *"negative thinking"* (PTSD) and *"poor concentration"* (MDD). Examples of emotional symptoms are *"intense mood fluctuations"* (BPD) and *"extreme anxiety in public transport"* (AP). Behavioral symptoms include *"engaging in risky behavior"* (BD) and *"excessively checking locks"* (OCD).

Figure 4. Categorization of symptoms into symptom categories. NB. since symptoms could be attributed to different categories at the same time, the sum of all symptoms in this graph exceeds 2199.

Figure 5 shows the distribution of the five most frequently discussed symptom categories (cognitive, emotional, behavioral, social, and physical) for all ten disorders. The data indicate that in BD, DID, OCD, SAD, and SP, cognitive symptoms were mentioned most frequently, whereas in MDD, BPD, PTSD and AP, emotional symptoms were the primary focus. Behavioral symptoms were mentioned most frequently in only one disorder, NPD. Social symptoms were mentioned relatively often in BPD and NPD compared to the other disorders (e.g., “unstable relationships” or “being interpersonally exploitative”). Physical symptoms were predominantly observed in videos about MDD and AP (e.g., “being tired” or “racing heart”).

Figure 5. Prevalence of five most frequent symptom categories in the ten mental disorders.

The figure in appendix C shows the distribution of symptoms across all ten categories for each disorder. It demonstrates that approximately 10% of the symptoms observed in videos about MDD, PTSD, and BD are related to sleep (i.e., “insomnia”, “hypersomnia”, or “nightmares”). Symptoms related to eating were mentioned almost exclusively in the context of MDD and BD (i.e., “change in appetite”). Self-care related symptoms were only mentioned in MDD and SP. Symptoms related to

coping mechanisms were mentioned mostly for BPD, with 14% of the symptoms in videos about BPD falling into this category (i.e., “*harmful impulsive behavior*”, “*self-harm*”, and “*suicidality*”).

Figure 6 shows the distribution of the DSM groups across symptom categories. Most symptoms within the ten categories are correct DSM criteria, but the percentages vary considerably between the different categories. For example, in more than 60% of the cases, the uncategorized symptoms in the ‘other’ category are not included in the DSM at all. These encompass symptoms that were, for instance, actions executed by others (e.g., “*being stereotyped as a bad person*” as a symptom of BPD) or symptoms that were very broad (“*psychosis*” as a symptom of BD). Moreover, approximately one-third of the symptoms in the physical, social, and behavioral category are not included in the DSM. In the case of physical symptoms, “*bodily aches and pains*” are frequently incorrectly mentioned as a symptom in nearly all ten mental disorders, apart from NPD and SP. The behavioral symptoms that are not included in the DSM are often either highly specific actions, such as “*looking at your phone first thing in the morning when you wake up*” in MDD, or very broad behaviors, such as “*delinquency*” or “*running away from home*” as symptoms of DID. Examples of incorrect social symptoms discussed in the videos include “*loving it when others are in pain*” for NPD and “*having difficulty making phone calls*” in SAD.

Figure 6. Distribution of DSM groups per symptom category

Explanation of symptoms in video

A total of 131 of the 315 videos (41.6%) included an explanation of the symptoms in the video. The results for each disorder can be found in table 5, which shows that the symptoms of NPD are explained most often (69.0% of videos) and symptoms of MDD least often (21.4% of videos). Mann-Whitney tests did not show a statistically significant correlation between the explanation of symptoms

and the three DSM group percentages for the whole dataset as well as per disorder after Bonferroni correction for multiple testing (see appendix D).

Target group mentioned in video

In 32 of the 315 videos, a specific target group was mentioned. Table 5 illustrates the distribution of mentioned target groups across the disorders. Examples of target groups include for example “*depression in black women*” and “*OCD in children*”. Notably, 50% of the videos focusing on a particular target group were related to NPD, with the video creators often providing guidance on “*how to recognize if your parent/partner/boss is a narcissist*”.

Terminology

The specific words that are used to reference the symptoms depicted in the video were registered to investigate whether the use of alternative words for ‘symptoms’ was associated with a higher number of non-DSM symptoms. Table 6 demonstrates that the majority of the symptoms were referenced as either ‘symptoms’ (128; 41%) or ‘signs’ (142; 45%). Other references were, for instance, small sentences like “what can X look/feel like” or “what is X?”. In some cases, the symptoms were contextualized within the individual’s experience, for example in “things I didn’t realize I did that were actually X”.

Table 6. Word references for symptoms

Word reference	Count
“Symptoms”	128 (40.6%)
“Signs”	142 (45.1%)
“Criteria”	3 (1.0%)
“What X can look/feel like”	13 (4.1%)
“What is X?”	4 (1.3%)
“Things I didn’t realize were X”	4 (1.3%)
“What X actually is”	6 (1.9%)
Other word references (features, indicators, characterizations, etc.)	7 (2.2%)
No reference	14 (4.4%)
Other	11 (3.5%)

Table 7 also shows the medians for the three DSM groups for videos that use the terms “symptoms”, “signs”, or another reference. In both cases of ‘symptoms’ and ‘signs’, most of the symptoms align with the DSM criteria. The percentage of DSM criteria is higher in videos that mention ‘symptoms’ (70%) compared to videos that mention ‘signs’ (52%). However, the number of symptoms that are not included in the DSM is higher for ‘signs’ than for ‘symptoms’. A statistically significant difference between these groups could not be tested due to the non-mutually exclusive categories, as a video could mention both ‘symptoms’ and ‘signs’.

Table 7. Word references & median DSM group percentages for total dataset

Word reference	Count	DSM-criteria	DSM-manifestation	Non-DSM
		Median (IQR)	Median (IQR)	Median (IQR)
“Symptoms”	128 (40.6%)	70.0% (41.3-100.0)	11.3% (0.0-33.3)	0.0% (0.0-28.3%)
“Signs”	142 (45.1%)	51.9% (25.0-83.3)	26.5% (23.6-45.5)	10.0% (0.0-33.3)
Other	62 (19.7%)	71.0% (33.3-100.0)	10.8% (0.0-28.6)	20.1% (0.0-34.4)

Figure 7 shows the prevalence of the use of the ‘symptoms’, ‘signs’ and other references for the total dataset and for every disorder. In a majority of the videos about BPD, SP, DID, BD, and PTSD, the ‘symptoms’ reference was used most often, whereas for MDD, NPD, and SAD, the ‘signs’ reference was used more frequently. For AP and OCD, other references were most prevalent.

Figure 7. Word references ‘symptoms’ & ‘signs’ per disorder

Creators

The account type of the video creators was registered (see figure 8) to investigate whether the expertise of a creator was correlated with spreading misinformation. The creators were assigned to one of five different expertise groups: no expertise, lived experience, coaching and alternative therapist expertise, medical expertise, and mental health expertise. The most prevalent creator expertise was no experience or only someone’s own lived experience as form of ‘expertise’ in 34% and 26% of the videos. Eight percent of the videos were created by various types of coaches (life/wellness/dating coaches) or alternative therapists (naturopathic doctor, hypnotherapist), who lack the requisite medical or psychological training to diagnose mental disorders. Lastly, 4% of the creators were medical professionals and 29% were mental health professionals with experience in diagnosing mental

disorders (i.e., clinical psychologist, licensed therapist, psychiatrist, psychiatric nurse practitioner). The creator expertise varied considerably depending on the disorder, as illustrated in figure 9.

Figure 8. Account types of the creators of the videos

Figure 9. Creator expertise of video creators for total dataset & per disorder. Mental health expertise includes therapists, psychologists, psychiatrists & psychiatric nurse practitioners.

Figure 10 and the corresponding table in appendix E show the distribution of the DSM groups across the creator expertise groups. The majority of creators tend to cite symptoms that align with the DSM criteria. However, 40% of the symptoms mentioned by coaches and alternative therapists are not included in the DSM, in comparison to 22% for both creators with no expertise or lived experience, and even lower percentages for medical and mental health professionals. The coaches and alternative therapists mention symptoms that are not in the DSM twice as often as creators with no expertise or only lived experience and four times as often as medical or mental health professionals. However, the results also demonstrate that even mental health professionals do not always post accurate information. Thirty percent of the symptoms mentioned by mental health professionals are not DSM criteria, of which ten percent are not even in the DSM at all.

Mann-Whitney testing was used to investigate whether there is a significant difference in the percentages of DSM criteria and non-DSM symptoms between the various expertise groups. This showed a significant difference in percentages of DSM for mental health professionals (70%) compared with creators with no expertise (57%) ($p = 0.003$), creators with lived experience (57%) ($p = 0.003$), and life coaches and alternative therapists (36%) ($p < 0.001$). Additionally, a significant difference was observed in the proportion of symptoms not included in the DSM for mental health professionals (10%) compared to creators with no expertise (22%) ($p < 0.001$), creators with lived experience (22%) ($p < 0.001$), and coaches and alternative therapists (40%) ($p < 0.001$). Moreover, a significant difference was found in the percentages of non-DSM symptoms between both creators with no expertise (22%) and medical professionals (7%) compared to coaches and alternative therapists (40%) (no expertise: $p = 0.003$; medical professional: $p = 0.001$). After Bonferroni correction for multiple testing, there was no significant difference in non-DSM symptom percentages for creators with lived experience (22%) compared to coaches and alternative therapists (40%) ($p = 0.006$; Bonferroni adjusted significance level: $p < 0.004$).

Figure 10. Distribution of DSM groups per creator expertise group. *NB. Percentages do not always add up to 100% because of rounding of the numbers.*

Disclaimers & sources

None of the users who were not mental health professionals included a disclaimer in the video mentioning that they lacked the professional qualifications to provide mental health advice or diagnose mental disorders. Furthermore, only 42 creators (13.3%) of videos included a disclaimer that discouraged self-diagnosis by warning viewers about the potential dangers of self-diagnosis or by stating that recognizing the symptoms in the video does not necessarily indicate that the viewer actually suffers from the disorder and encouraging viewers to seek professional help instead of self-diagnosing. Of these 42 creators, 17 were mental health professionals (40.5%), 1 was a medical professional (2.4%), 3 were coaches or alternative therapists (7.1%), 13 had lived experience (31.0%), and 8 creators had no expertise (19.0%).

Only 65 out of 315 creators (20.6%) mentioned a source for the information they provided in their video. The majority of the sources were referenced in videos about PTSD (31.0%), whereas only one video about SAD included a source (4.8%). See appendix F for an overview of the use of sources per disorder. More than half of the sources were infographics that were depicted in the video (40; 61.5%). However, only 13 of these infographics (20.0%) were derived from sources with expertise in mental health, such as mental health organizations. See appendix G for an overview of all the different sources that were referenced in the videos.

User engagement

The user engagement metrics were quantified in number of views, likes, comments, shares, and saves. The videos had a median number of 94.6k views (range: 256 - 11.2m), 4.3k likes (range: 7 - 1.8m), 83 comments (range: 0 - 12.1k), 917 shares (2 - 144.9k), and 209 saves (range: 0 - 38.3k) per video. See appendix H for the results per disorder. To assess whether there was a correlation between the DSM groups and user engagement metrics, a Spearman's Rank Correlation test was performed. No statistically significant correlation between any of the user engagement metrics and the three DSM groups was found (see appendix I), indicating that there was no significant difference in user engagement between videos with correct DSM criteria and videos with non-DSM symptoms.

Discussion

Substantial inconsistency with DSM criteria

This study aimed to assess the reliability of TikTok videos about the symptoms of mental disorders in order to gain a better overview of the misinformation that is circulating on TikTok. In this study, 59% of the presented symptoms align with the official DSM-5-TR criteria for psychiatric disorders. Twenty percent of the symptoms were not the specific DSM criteria, but direct manifestations of these criteria mentioned as associated diagnostic features of the disorders in the DSM-5-TR textbook. Such symptoms were frequently presented in a more generalized manner as very broad behaviors or were highly specific examples, which both contribute to an inaccurate portrayal of the symptoms of these disorders on TikTok. The final 21% of the symptoms were not referenced in the DSM at all. Especially videos about SAD, NPD, AP, OCD, and DID contained high percentages of symptoms that are not in the DSM. These findings align with the results from other recent studies on misinformation about mental health and specific mental disorders on TikTok (Aragon-Guevara et al., 2023; Munoz et al., 2024; PlushCare, 2022; Tadross & Griffin, 2023; Yeung et al., 2022). Although over 50% of the symptoms in this study correspond to the official DSM criteria, the relatively high prevalence of videos portraying DSM manifestations and non-DSM symptoms as legitimate symptoms of a disorder is a cause for concern. In line with the selective exposure theory, viewers' inaccurate beliefs are continuously confirmed by repeated exposure to these inaccuracies, which is further reinforced by TikTok's algorithm. This problematic process contributes significantly to the risk of inaccurate self-diagnosis among users.

This risk is even further increased by the absence of information and nuance regarding the minimum duration and severity of symptoms. Only 7% of the videos in this study provided information on the minimum duration required for a diagnosis, and a mere 3% mentioned that for a diagnosis to be established, the symptoms must be severe enough to significantly affect an individual's daily life and functioning. In addition, less than half of the videos provided an explanation of the symptoms. This contributes considerably to the misleading oversimplified image of mental disorders on TikTok, as this presents symptoms of these disorders without the fitting context and nuances that are so important for correctly diagnosing mental disorders. The lack of information regarding the minimum duration or severity of symptoms of a mental disorder increases the likelihood of users relating to the depicted symptoms, leading to an increased tendency of them incorrectly attributing their own behavior to this mental disorder. In combination with seemingly small nuances like talking about 'signs' instead of 'symptoms' and by portraying mental disorders as simplified checklists, the probability of viewers resonating with the videos will increase even further. This all contributes to the problematic trend of medicalization of normal human experiences of mental distress and unnecessarily increases the risk it poses to our youth.

The differences in prevalence of distinct symptom categories observed in the TikTok videos can also prove to be misleading for viewers. While not all mental disorders have an equal distribution of cognitive, emotional, and behavioral symptoms in their DSM criteria, the evident discrepancies in prevalence of certain symptom categories over others contribute to a distorted picture of the true spectrum of symptoms of mental disorders. For example, approximately 50% of the symptoms mentioned in videos about BPD were emotional symptoms, even though only one-third of the DSM criteria for this disorder fall into this category. This illustrates the misleading framing and misrepresentation of mental disorders on TikTok, with a tendency to emphasize certain criteria while disregarding others. Additionally, certain symptom categories more frequently exhibited symptoms that are not included in the DSM: in particular, physical symptoms mentioned in the videos about nearly all ten disorders often did not align with the DSM criteria. In addition, behavioral and social symptoms frequently exhibited inaccuracies, ranging from highly specific to extremely broad behaviors.

Lack of mental health expertise among creators

Approximately one-third of the creators in this study were mental health professionals, with even half of the creators of videos about AP, OCD, and SAD being a mental health professional. Together with medical professionals, mental health professionals most frequently shared symptoms that aligned with the DSM criteria. The relatively high prevalence of mental health professionals in this study is in stark contrast with prior research by PlushCare (2022), where only 9% of the creators were mental health professionals. This may be indicative of a positive trend which suggests that mental health professionals are becoming more active on social media to spread accurate scientific information to counter the circulating misinformation.

However, the majority of creators in this study either lacked expertise or based the information in their videos solely on personal experience. While this does not inherently imply that the information shared is inaccurate, it may increase the risk of omitting critical nuances necessary for accurately diagnosing mental disorders. In addition, none of the creators without mental health expertise informed viewers of their lack of qualifications for providing mental health advice and only a minority of videos included a warning for viewers to refrain from self-diagnosis and to seek professional help instead. Alarming, some creators even encouraged viewers to self-diagnose, thereby directly contributing to the potential harm associated with incorrect self-diagnosis.

The creators with the highest probability of spreading misinformation on TikTok were coaches and alternative therapists. Their videos exhibited a much higher prevalence of symptoms not included in the DSM compared to both mental health professionals and creators without expertise. This was particularly evident in the case of NPD: one-third of the videos about NPD is posted by coaches, who

frequently encourage their viewers to diagnose individuals in their immediate environment with NPD. This trend considerably contributes to the perpetuation of stereotypes and the spread of misinformation about NPD on social media and in society at large. The reliability of the content disseminated by coaches and alternative therapists on TikTok has yet to be investigated, but mental health professionals have publicly expressed their discontent with the misinformation and pseudoscience that is promoted by these creators (Grunewald, 2024; Stea, 2024; Sung, 2021). They state that non-expert creators are exploiting the widespread interest in mental health content for their own benefit by posting misinformation to attract more viewers (Sung, 2021). However, the veracity of this claim remains uncertain. The present study did not identify a significant difference in user engagement with misleading videos compared to videos containing accurate information.

Limitations & future research

The biggest strength of this research is that it is one of the first to research misinformation across multiple mental disorders and to specifically analyze symptom-related content on TikTok. However, several limitations must be considered when interpreting the results. First of all, the TikTok algorithm may have influenced data collection despite efforts to minimize its impact. This may have resulted in search results that are personalized for the researcher's location (i.e., The Netherlands) and user profile (i.e., account of a 15-year-old). It was, however, impossible to work around this limitation, as the algorithm restricts systematic searches through all videos on the platform.

Furthermore, this research represents only a snapshot of the fraction of TikTok's large repository of videos on mental disorder symptoms. More research is needed to gain a fuller understanding of the amount of misinformation on TikTok regarding other mental disorders and other elements of the mental health literacy framework like causes and treatments. Additionally, future studies should explore longer existing social media platforms that are popular among young adolescents, such as Instagram and X (Twitter). Particularly Instagram Reels is of interest, as it employs similar video scrolling features and algorithms as TikTok to track user preferences.

To better understand how to protect adolescents from misinformation about mental disorder symptoms on social media platforms like TikTok, it is crucial to investigate to what extent exposure to these videos impact their attitudes and knowledge about mental disorders. Since this study does not measure this impact directly, we can only speculate about the effects of the misinformation in these videos. However, Dewak (2023) conducted an interview study with a slightly older demographic (young adults aged 19-26) to examine the effects of self-diagnosis content on Instagram and TikTok, revealing that their experiences varied from mostly skepticism about the reliability of information in the videos, to some also feeling validated by content that resonated with them. Further research is necessary to determine whether the experiences of young adolescents differ from those of young adults.

Another limitation of this study is the difficulty of determining the accuracy of the information presented in the videos based on the DSM. Although the DSM-5-TR is a widely used diagnostic tool for both clinicians and researchers, it has received criticism for lacking empirical scientific support, neglecting sociocultural contexts, and medicalizing normal experiences of distress by oversimplifying mental disorders into simple checklists (Bredström, 2019; Wakefield, 2016). The DSM criteria are often vague and general, which made it challenging to objectively code the symptoms into the appropriate DSM group. This difficulty became evident during the intercoder reliability check. As is also the case in the clinical world, discrepancies between the coders arose from different interpretations of specific terms or vague descriptions in the videos. The only way to reach sufficient agreement was by adhering very closely to the text in the DSM handbook. However, the DSM's supplementary descriptions of associated features and examples are not an exhaustive list of possible manifestations of DSM criteria, which may have resulted in an overestimation of the non-DSM symptoms in this study. Additionally, since neither of the coders was a trained mental health professional with experience in diagnosing mental disorders, there is a possibility that the coding of symptoms into the DSM groups may not have been consistently accurate.

Conclusions & practical implications

In conclusion, this study contributes to a better understanding of the prevalence and dissemination of mental health misinformation on TikTok. The findings reveal a substantial amount of misinformation about mental disorder symptoms, which contributes to the growing number of adolescents self-diagnosing through oversimplified and misleading checklists on TikTok. The content frequently contains inaccuracies and lacks the essential nuances and context necessary for accurately diagnosing mental disorders. This misinformation contributes to the medicalization of normal emotional distress and may reinforce societal stigma surrounding mental disorders.

These insights lead to several practical implications for mental health professionals, social media users, and social media platforms. Both clinicians and social media users should be vigilant about the misinformation circulating on social media and be open to discussing the implications of self-diagnosis content if deemed necessary. Moreover, clinicians should consider increasing their presence and visibility on TikTok to help disseminate accurate health information on the platform. Furthermore, social media platforms need to implement stricter, proactive measures to curb the spread of misinformation online. While TikTok already regulates content related to eating disorders and suicide, similar regulations should be extended to other mental health conditions and incorporate warnings about potential misinformation to better protect their users.

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Appendix

Content list:

A. TikTok hashtags	30
B. Codebook	31
C. Symptom categorization per disorder	40
D. Correlation explanation of symptoms in video & DSM groups	40
E. Creator expertise groups	41
F. Use of sources per disorder	41
G. Overview of types of referenced sources	42
H. Engagement metrics per disorder	42
I. Correlation user engagement metrics & DSM groups	43

Appendix A. Included mental disorders & overview of checked hashtags

Disorder	Posts (TikTok)	Views (scraper)	Hashtag choice
Depression			
#depression	2.7 million	19.5 billion	1
#MDD	52.7 thousand	386.5 million	2
#majordepressivedisorder	18.1 thousand	97 million	3
Bipolar disorder			
#bipolar	914.2 thousand	6.4 billion	1
#bipolaridorder	197 thousand	1.6 billion	2
Agoraphobia			
#agoraphobia	29.6 thousand	263.6 million	1
Social anxiety disorder			
#socialanxiety	261.4 thousand	3.4 billion	1
#socialanxietydisorder	5491	48.2 million	2
Borderline			
#bpd	1.7 million	14.1 billion	1
#borderlinepersonalitydisorder	351.9 thousand	3 billion	2
#borderline	347.2 thousand	3.5 billion	3
Narcissistic personality disorder			
#narcissist	1.1 million	14.2 billion	1
#narcissism	406.4 thousand	5.5 billion	2
#narcissistic	184.4 thousand	2.7 billion	3
#npd	146.2 thousand	2.3 billion	4

#narcissisticpersonalitydisorder	38.4 thousand	558.7 million	5
Schizophrenia			
#schizophrenic	83.1 thousand	2.1 billion	1
#schizophrenia	54.9 thousand	1.3 billion	2
OCD			
#OCD	350.2 thousand	7.7 billion	1
#obsessivecompulsivedisorder	21 thousand	504.1 million	2
DID			
#DID	712.8 thousand	3.4 billion	1
#dissociativeidentitydisorder	245.8 thousand	1.8 billion	2
PTSD			
#ptsd	1.2 million	8.5 billion	1
#ptsdawareness	361.7 thousand	1.4 billion	2
#posttraumaticstressdisorder	9099	62.1 million	3

Appendix B. Codebook

NB. Questions are about the **content (spoken word & text on screen)** as well as the **caption** of the video!

Disorder

Q1. Which mental disorder is the TikTok video about?

- [1] Major depressive disorder
- [2] Bipolar disorder
- [3] Social anxiety disorder
- [4] Agoraphobia
- [5] Narcissistic personality disorder
- [6] Borderline personality disorder
- [7] Post-traumatic stress disorder
- [8] Obsessive-compulsive disorder
- [9] Dissociative identity disorder
- [10] Schizophrenia

Symptoms

Q2. How many symptoms are listed?

Write down the number

Q3. Which word(s) are used to refer to the mentioned symptoms?

E.g., 3 signs of OCD, 5 symptoms of depression, etc.

NB. Some videos include a further explanation per symptom, do not include the words/references that are mentioned during this explanation!

Check all that apply (don't forget to check the caption); if multiple separate by comma (e.g., 1,2).

- [1] Symptoms
- [2] Signs
- [3] Hints
- [4] Other (specify)

Q4. Are the mentioned symptoms further explained verbally in the video or just mentioned without any further description or explanation?

[0] No explanation (i.e., only mentioning the symptoms)

[1] Explanation (i.e., mentioning the symptom and giving more context or examples)

Per symptom:

Q5. What is the symptom?

Write down

Q6. Is the mentioned symptom a literal quote or direct synonym of a DSM-V-TR criterium of this mental disorder? (check symptom list in appendix)

[0] No / [1] Yes

If Yes – skip to Q9

Q7. Is the mentioned symptom an associated feature or direct manifestation of a DSM-V symptom criterium of this mental disorder, as mentioned in the DSM-V-TR handbook? (check symptom list in appendix)

[0] No / [1] Yes

If Yes – skip to Q9

Q8. If the mentioned symptom is not featured in the official DSM-V-TR criteria or the accompanied text in the DSM-V-TR handbook, how specific is this symptom?

[1] High specificity: very specific single action/emotion, for instance with a time/frequency or location indication

- E.g., reaching for your phone first thing in the morning; constantly looking at your phone during dinner*
- [2] Medium specificity: more specific, measurable action (using words like ‘more’/’higher’) but no specific single occurrence
E.g., spending more time on your phone; sleeping more than usual
- [3] Low specificity: broad description of action/behavior/emotion
E.g., phone-use; paranoia; nervous fidgeting

Q9. What category does the mentioned symptom best fit under?

Check all that apply; if multiple separate with a comma (e.g., 1,2)

- [1] Emotional (e.g., sadness, irritability, mood swings)
- [2] Behavioral (e.g., showing certain behavior like neglecting responsibilities, nervous acts like nail biting, refraining from activities)
- [3] Social, inter-personal (e.g., no desire to socialize, social withdrawal)
- [4] Physical (e.g., pain, fatigue, palpitations)
- [5] Cognitive (e.g., lack of attention, memory problems)
- [6] Related to sleep (e.g., sleeping more or less than normal, trouble falling asleep, change in day/night rhythm)
- [7] Related to eating (e.g., eating more or less than usual, binge eating)
- [8] Related to hygiene and self-care (e.g., neglecting personal hygiene like showering, brushing teeth, wearing clean clothes, brushing hair)
- [9] Coping mechanisms (e.g., gambling, spending a lot of money, substance use)
- [10] Other: write down (open coding)

➔ Repeat Q5-Q9 for all mentioned symptoms. If all mentioned symptoms in the video have been coded, continue to Q10.

Other diagnostic criteria

Q10. Is the duration and/or frequency of the symptoms mentioned in the video?

Can be recognized by time references. E.g., every day, for two weeks, lifelong, etc.

[0] No / [1] Yes

If No – skip to Q13

Q11. (If Yes) What is the mentioned duration and/or frequency?

Specify: (open coding)

Q12. Is it explicitly stated that there is a specific minimum duration and/or frequency of the symptoms as an additional diagnostic criterium?

*Also, if the word 'criterium' is not explicitly mentioned: e.g., 'the symptoms **should be present** for at least 2 weeks' would also be a 'yes' for this question.*

NB. Not solely mentioning that a duration and/or frequency. It should be implied that the symptoms must have a minimum duration and/or frequency in order to be diagnosed with this disorder.

[0] No / [1] Yes

Q13. Is it explicitly stated that 'a significant impact on daily functioning' or a similar statement on impact on daily functioning is an additional diagnostic criterium?

*Also, if the word 'criterium' is not mentioned explicitly: e.g., 'the symptoms **should** have a significant impact on daily life/functioning' would also be a 'yes' for this question.*

NB. Not solely mentioning that there is an impact on daily functioning. It should be implied that the symptoms must have a significant impact on daily functioning in order to be diagnosed with this disorder.

[0] No / [1] Yes

If No –skip to Q15

Q14. (If Yes) What category of daily functioning is mentioned?

Check all that apply; if multiple separate by comma (e.g., 1,2)

- [1] Impairment in social functioning & relationships
- [2] Impairment in daily activities (e.g., doing groceries, cooking food)
- [3] Impairment in occupational functioning (work)
- [4] Other (specify)

Co-morbidity

Q15. Is another mental disorder mentioned as co-morbidity in the video?

E.g., eating disorder, depression, anxiety disorder.

NB. Only when the specific disorder is mentioned (e.g., depression), not if only symptoms of that disorder are mentioned (e.g., 'low mood', 'depressive symptoms')

[0] No / [1] Yes

If No – skip to Q17

Q16. (If Yes) Which disorder is mentioned as co-morbidity?

Write down (open coding)

Context

Q17. Does the video mention symptoms for a specific target group instead of the general population?

E.g., symptoms of depression in men/women/children/people of color etc.

[0] No / [1] Yes

If No – skip to Q19

Q18. What target group is mentioned in the video?

Write down the target group (open coding)

Q19. Are the symptoms mentioned in the context of an individual or in general?

*Individualized: if the focus is on a **specified individual person** with a mental health condition (e.g., creator **themselves**, relative, friend, famous person). NOT if creator is pretending to have mental health conditions).*

➔ *Examples: signs/symptoms I experience from **my** OCD; things I didn't realize were actually **my** OCD, signs **I** had OCD that were overlooked, POV: your relative/friend is showing signs of OCD, signs of OCD of this famous person.*

Generalized: symptoms in general without mention of a specific person/without creator saying it's their own experience.

➔ *Examples: 3 signs you have OCD; 3 symptoms of OCD you didn't know about; hidden/early/lesser-known signs of OCD; OCD may look like...; 3 symptoms of OCD...*

[1] Individualized/personal experience (self)

[2] Individualized/personal experience (relative or close friend)

[3] Individualized/no personal experience (well-known person, celebrity)

[4] Generalized

[5] Mix of both individualized and generalized

If [4] - skip to Q21

Q20. Is it emphasized in the text in caption, on screen, or in spoken word that this is a personal experience and thus not generalizable to the rest of the population?

[0] No / [1] Yes

Q21. Does the video discourage or encourage self-diagnosis (in video or caption)?

- [1] Discourage (i.e., disclaimers about the dangers of self-diagnosis, stating that recognizing the symptoms in the video does not necessarily mean that you actually have the disorder and that you should seek help from medical or mental health professionals instead)
- [2] Encourage (i.e., statements such as ‘how many symptoms do you recognize?’ or ‘send this video to a friend that does these things’)
- [3] Not mentioned

Creator characteristics

Q22. What is the TikTok account’s identity?

- [1] Individual creator (represented by 1 person making original content)
- [2] Group account (represented by 2 or more visible people making original content, without affiliation to larger organization)
- [3] Business/organization account (not generated by individual but by company, business, or organization)
- [4] Television- or internet-based news (generated by a news outlet, created for or reposted on TikTok)
- [5] Anonymous account (not clearly represented by an individual creator, business or news outlet)
- [6] Other (specify)

If [3], [4], [5] or [6] – skip to Q26

Q23. Does/do the creator(s) mention their (mental) health-related occupation?

Mentioned in the video, caption of the video, TikTok account name, or account bio.

E.g., psychotherapist, medical doctor, life coach, homeopathist, orthomolecular therapist etc.

[0] No / [1] Yes

If No, skip to Q25-Q26 but skip Q27.

If Yes, continue with Q24-Q26 but skip Q27.

Q24. What is the mentioned (mental) health-related occupation?

Write down (open coding)

Q25. Does/do the creator(s) mention their own lived experience with mental illness?

[0] No / [1] Yes

Q26. Does the video contain a disclaimer that the creator is not qualified to give medical advice?

[0] No

[1] No, because the creator is a qualified mental health professional (= psychotherapist, psychologist, or psychiatrist)

[2] Yes

Q27. In case of an organization: what is the nature of the business/organization represented by the account?

E.g., educational organization, medical center/hospital, mental health organization, marketing company, charity, etc.

Write down 'unknown' if not mentioned in video, caption of video, TikTok account name, or account bio.

Write down (open coding)

Sources

Q28. Does the video include sources for its mental health information?

The creator also counts as source if it is a verified mental health expert (psychotherapist, psychologist, psychiatrist) or if they talk about their own experience (experience expert)

[0] No / [1] Yes

If No – skip to Q30

Q29. (If Yes) What type(s) of sources are used?

If the creator is a mental health expert this does count as a quote from an expert. If the (non-expert) creator is talking about their own experience this counts as an experience expert.

Check all that apply; if multiple separate by a comma (e.g., 1,2)

[1] Quote expert (including creator if they have expertise)

[2] Quote experience expert (including creator if they have lived experience with mental health issues)

[3] Published research paper

[4] Published scientific/medical book (e.g., DSM handbook)

[5] Other books (self-help books)

[6] Internet website (content written by medical professionals)

[7] Internet website (not written by medical professionals)

[8] Infographic with source

[9] Infographic without source or from non-mental health professionals

[10] Other published media (podcast, video)

[11] Other (specify)

Video characteristics

Q30. What type of content is featured in the TikTok?

Check all that apply; if multiple separate by a comma (e.g., 1,2)

- [1] Creator/narrator discussing personal experience/experience in their direct environment in spoken word or text
- [2] Creator/narrator discussing symptoms in general in spoken word or text (thus not focused on a particular individual)
- [3] Re-enactment, serious (recognized by serious mood, heavy topics, serious music/sound)
- [4] Re-enactment, humoristic (recognized by over-exaggeration, face effects, funny music/sound)
- [5] Animation
- [6] Picture slide show
- [7] Other (specify)

Causes

Q31. Does the TikTok mention potential causes for the mentioned mental disorder?

[0] No / [1] Yes

If No – skip to Q33

Q32. (If Yes) In which category do the mentioned cause(s) belong?

Check all that apply; if multiple separate by a comma (e.g., 1,2)

- [1] Biological: “Depression is a brain disease/chemical imbalance.”
- [2] Environmental: “Depression is caused by stressful life events like childhood trauma, illness or substance abuse.”
- [3] Cognitive: “Depression is driven by negative thinking styles”
- [4] Personal weakness: “Depression is caused by a person’s lack of resilience or having a weak brain”
- [5] Lifestyle: “Depression is caused by diet or lack of exercise”
- [6] Other: specify (e.g., “Depression is caused by lack of vitamin D”)

Mental health interventions

Q33. Does the TikTok mention a mental health intervention that can help/reduce the symptoms?

[0] No / [1] Yes

If No – skip to end

Q34. (If Yes) Which mental health interventions are mentioned?

Check all that apply; if multiple separate by a comma (e.g., 1,2)

- [1] Medication (as prescribed by healthcare professionals, e.g., antidepressants)
- [2] Therapy (psycho-, behavioral-, cognitive-therapy) by mental health professionals
- [3] Therapy by non-mental health professionals such as life/mental coach
- [4] Alternative therapy (e.g., orthomolecular-, hypno-, acupuncture-, animal-assisted therapy)
- [5] Mindfulness, meditation
- [6] Exercise (incl. yoga)
- [7] Alternative medicine (e.g., homeopathy, herbs, supplements, ketamine, essential oils)
- [8] Lifestyle change (e.g., diet, exercise)
- [9] Support (e.g., talking to loved ones or teachers at school, expressing feelings/emotions)
- [10] Other (specify)

Q35. Is the effectiveness of the mentioned mental health intervention(s) mentioned?

E.g., the treatment is effective, this therapy does not work for this disorder, etc.

If multiple interventions are mentioned, write down 0/1 followed by ('intervention') for each one.

[0] No / [1] Yes

If No – skip to end

Q36. What is the creator's/video's opinion regarding the effectiveness of the mentioned mental health intervention(s)?

If multiple interventions are mentioned, write down 1/2/3/4 followed by ('intervention') for each one.

- [1] Positive (i.e., this intervention works, is recommended)
- [2] Negative (i.e., this intervention does not work, is not recommended)
- [3] Neutral (i.e., mentioning interventions but not specifically mentioning its effectiveness)
- [4] Mixed (i.e., creator/video is both positive and negative about the intervention)

Appendix C. Distribution of symptom categories per disorder

Appendix D. Mann-Whitney U measures & corresponding p-values of correlations between explanation of symptoms in videos and DSM groups

Disorder	DSM criteria U (p-value)	DSM manifestations U (p-value)	Not in DSM U (p-value)
Total	11649 (p = 0.608)	11481 (p = 0.460)	11714 (p = 0.649)
MDD	130.0 (p = 0.587)	136.5 (p = 0.718)	134.5 (p = 0.673)
BPD	121.5 (p = 0.010)	117.5 (p = 0.005)	176.5 (p = 0.210)
PTSD	136.5 (p = 0.494)	140.0 (p = 0.570)	144.5 (p = 0.652)
NPD	158.5 (p = 0.419)	163.5 (p = 0.501)	152.0 (p = 0.332)
BD	110.0 (p = 0.146)	115.0 (p = 0.192)	99.5 (p = 0.074)
DID	48.5 (p = 0.654)	29.5 (p = 0.072)	45.0 (p = 0.512)
OCD	30.5 (p = 0.085)	41.5 (p = 0.349)	32.5 (p = 0.114)
SAD	54.5 (p = 0.973)	34.5 (p = 0.152)	50.5 (p = 0.756)
SP	49.0 (p = 0.860)	33.0 (p = 0.595)	46.5 (p = 0.697)
AP	49.5 (p = 0.754)	52.0 (p = 0.917)	41.0 (p = 0.382)

NB. Bonferroni correction for multiple testing resulted in cut-off p-value of <0.0015. No significant p-values were found.

Appendix E. Creator expertise distribution per disorder

Disorder	Mental health expertise	Professional health expertise	Non-prof health expertise	Lived experience	No expertise
	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)
Total	92 (29.2%)	12 (3.8%)	24 (7.6%)	81 (25.7%)	106 (33.7%)
MDD	17 (40.5%)	4 (9.5%)	1 (2.4%)	4 (9.5%)	16 (38.1%)
BPD	8 (19.0%)	1 (2.4%)	0	18 (42.9%)	15 (35.7%)
PTSD	10 (23.8%)	2 (4.8%)	2 (4.8%)	7 (16.7%)	21 (50.0%)
NPD	6 (14.3%)	1 (2.4%)	14 (33.3%)	2 (4.8%)	19 (45.2%)
BD	8 (19.0%)	2 (4.8%)	1 (2.4%)	19 (45.2%)	12 (28.6%)
DID	2 (9.5%)	0	1 (4.8%)	9 (42.9%)	9 (42.9%)
OCD	10 (47.6%)	0	3 (14.3%)	6 (28.6%)	2 (9.5%)
SAD	10 (47.6%)	0	1 (4.8%)	3 (14.3%)	7 (33.3%)
SP	9 (42.9%)	2 (9.5%)	0	8 (38.1%)	2 (9.5%)
AP	12 (57.1%)	0	1 (4.8%)	5 (23.8%)	3 (14.3%)

Appendix F. Percentages of use of sources per disorder

Disorders	Number of videos with sources
	N (%)
PTSD	13 of 42 (31.0%)
AP	6 of 21 (28.6%)
OCD	5 of 21 (23.8%)
BD	9 of 42 (21.4%)
MDD	8 of 42 (19.0%)
BPD	8 of 42 (19.0%)
SP	4 of 21 (19.0%)
DID	3 of 21 (14.3%)
NPD	4 of 42 (9.5%)
SAD	1 of 21 (4.8%)

NB. Ordered from highest to lowest percentage

Appendix G. Overview of types of referenced sources

Abbreviations: MHE = mental health expertise; MHP = mental health professional

Appendix H. Engagement metrics for entire dataset & per disorder

Disorder	Views	Likes	Comments	Saves	Shares
	Median (range)	Median (range)	Median (range)	Median (range)	Median (range)
Total	94.6k (256 – 11.2m)	4.3k (7 – 1.8m)	83 (0 – 12.1k)	917 (2 – 144.9k)	209 (0 – 38.3k)
MDD	297.1k (14.6k – 11.2m)	31k (489 – 1.8m)	357 (0 – 10.4k)	3.0k (72 – 144.9k)	705 (9 – 38.3k)
SAD	241.1k (3.9k – 9.0m)	21.7k (170 – 1.8m)	163 (2 – 12.1k)	2.1k (34 – 82.0k)	327 (3 – 19.1k)
BPD	221.5k (5.7k – 5.1m)	19.3k (243 – 939.4k)	156 (2 – 8.8k)	4.4k (58 – 80.2k)	631 (8 – 18.5k)
NPD	175.2k (3.2k – 4.6m)	6.3k (83 – 278.6k)	158 (1 – 5.5k)	1.7k (16 – 43.3k)	570 (7 – 36.9k)
BD	81.9k (506 – 3.4m)	3.8k (41 – 191.6k)	60 (0 – 2.4k)	730 (6 – 27.4k)	124 (0 – 11.5k)
OCD	73.6k (7.8k – 2.3m)	2.5k (247 – 167.5k)	37 (0 – 1.8k)	546 (0 – 2.1k)	109 (5 – 16.8k)
SP	48.8k (1.0k – 6.3m)	2.2k (78 – 175.3k)	93 (1 – 4.5k)	584 (10 – 28.3k)	85 (0 – 13.7k)
PTSD	32.0k (497 – 1.7m)	1.5k (21 – 200.1k)	18 (0 – 1.2k)	210 (4 – 59.2k)	46 (0 – 8.0k)
AP	20.5k (432 – 2.0m)	629 (27 – 40.8k)	33 (0 – 511)	99 (2 – 8.8k)	36 (0 – 3.4k)
DID	16.7k (256 – 412.7k)	636 (7 – 8.5k)	12 (0 – 229)	99 (2 – 8.8k)	12 (0 – 393)

Appendix I. Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient & corresponding p-values of correlations between user engagement metrics and DSM groups

	DSM criteria	DSM manifestations	Not in DSM
	R (p-value)	R (p-value)	R (p-value)
Views	0.034 (p = 0.552)	-0.008 (p = 0.887)	-0.073 (0.199)
Likes	0.028 (p = 0.623)	-0.006 (p = 0.920)	-0.068 (p = 0.232)
Comments	0.035 (p = 0.538)	-0.025 (p = 0.660)	-0.082 (p = 0.149)
Shares	0.008 (p = 0.890)	-0.003 (p = 0.952)	-0.027 (p = 0.631)
Saves	0.003 (p = 0.961)	-0.001 (p = 0.992)	-0.020 (p = 0.724)

NB. No statistically significant p-values.